

PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE IN FUTURE TEACHERS PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS OF FORMATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7828466>

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada bugungi kunda jamiyatda amalga oshirilayotgan islohatlar talablariga to'la javob beruvchi, ishlab chiqarish sohasida yuzaga kelgan raqobatga bardoshli, keskin o'zgarishlarga moslasha oluvchi, shuningdek, mehnat bozorida mutaxassislar malakasiga qo'yilayotgan talablar darajasida samarali faoliyat yurituvchi pedagog shaxsni shakllantirishning nazariy asoslari yoritilgan. Maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida tarbiyachining kasbiy mahoratiga e'tibor berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: kompetentlik, umumiy, maxsus, ekstremal, metodik, ijtimoiy, shaxsiy, kasbiy kompetentlik.

Abstract: This article deals with what is happening in society today fully responding to the requirements of reforms, which arose in the field of production resistant to competition, able to adapt to sudden changes, as well as labor effective activity at the level of requirements for the qualifications of specialists in the market the theoretical foundations of the formation of a leading pedagogic personality are explained. Before school in educational institutions, attention is

paid to the professional skills of educators.

Key words: competence, general, special, extreme, methodical, social, personal, professional competence.

Аннотация: В данной статье речь идет о том, что происходит в обществе сегодня полностью отвечая требованиям реформ, возникших в сфере производства устойчивы к конкуренции, способны приспосабливаться к резким изменениям, а также к труду объяснены теоретические основы формирования педагогической личности, эффективно работающей на уровне требований к квалификации специалистов на рынке. Уделяется внимание профессиональному мастерству воспитателей дошкольных образовательных учреждений.

Ключевые слова: компетентность, общая, специальная, экстремальная, методическая, социальная, личная, профессиональная компетентность.

Competence is required from a pedagogue as a sign of professional skill is a feature. The meaning of the word "competence" is awareness, authority, one's field is determined by having a comprehensive understanding and experience. Competence is a personal quality, pedagogical activity and social in different situations is the ability, knowledge, skills and competence expressed in life. The terms "competence" and "competence" are cognate words, they are western appeared in scientific literature in the late 60s and 70s of the 20th century. The term "competence" has been used in national pedagogy since the 90s of the 20th century began to be used.

Professional competence of the educator of the preschool educational organization pedagogues' personal qualities in the formation and development of professional competence it is necessary to pay attention to the coordination with the characteristics. Educator behavior and his interests affect his professional growth. Love for his profession, constant search and movement through clear goals professional competence improves. Qualities indicating the professional competence of the educator are listed as follows:

- Having knowledge of pedagogy and psychology;
- Work on yourself;
- Ability to plan the educational process, evaluate children's knowledge;
- Formation of motivation in children;
- Knowledge of ICT;
- Innovation in educational activities;
- Perfect knowledge of children's age characteristics and individual ways of working;
- To be aware of foreign languages and one of the modern fields.

Self-analysis of the formation of professional competence, necessary things understanding, self-development planning, setting goals, tasks, self covers the steps to correct display errors. In determining the development of professional competence in educators, professional a competency module is created. That is, it is the organizer of professional competence. Before identifying the important components, its overall picture is created. Professional love and curiosity about the

profession before acquiring knowledge and concepts is determined. When the owner of a professional activity does not call his activity labor, if it is viewed as a hobby, then creative ability will develop. Professional competency module is professional knowledge and understanding with interest and enthusiasm professional skills based on acquisition, application of knowledge in practical activities and from the formation of skills and the achievement of the assessment of activity as a value consists of becoming the owner of this module is different in professional activity to develop the ability to automatically use effective solutions in situations. Preschool education is as important as preparing a child for a new stage of life performs the task. The initial stage of the child's entry into social life naturally, it will not be easy. Because a child is only a parent goes out of scope and joins the collective life. This process is different for children with individual characteristics has different effects. The task of the educator is the child's physical and mental based on his characteristics, accustoming him to a collective way of life and in the community is the formation of skills to live freely.

In conclusion, it can be said that preschool educational organizations in the formation and development of the professional competencies of educators with deep acquisition of knowledge based on theoretical and practical experiences depends. Self-development according to the scale of professional competence of educators on the basis of their progress, they will be able to acquire professional competence. Constantly achieving professional growth and improving professional skills, professional being able to realize one's inner potential in the activity,

independently preparation for organization of professional-pedagogical activity, usual professional-pedagogical correctly solving tasks and realistically evaluating the results of one's work possession of qualifications, new knowledge and skills in the specialty to learn consistently measure their capabilities based on stages such as ability transfer and on this basis set new tasks and goals possible.

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